

Technical Guideline Series

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Sustainable Use Assessment Directory

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This page is designed to help navigate through all the documents of the sustainable use of wild species assessment, such as the data management reports, figures and all accompanying documents.

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- Full report

Summary for policymakers

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Glossary

- SUA glossary

Underlying bibliographic data and research materials

- SUA Zotero library